

public review: draft data guidance

The ipaast project is inviting comments on drafts of guidance prepared on a range of remote and near surface sensing data types used in applications across agri-environment and archaeological applications. These documents are intended to improve technical and semantic interoperability of these data types.

Each document includes sections which describe the type of data in general terms, make recommendations for minimal metadata and thematic tags (from standard vocabularies), describe common data processing stages, explain the scope of applications of the data, and provide a short bibliography of relevant literature.

Draft data guidance documents

[draft_standard_optrx_data_forcomment < https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/draft_standard_optrx_data_forcomment.docx>](https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/draft_standard_optrx_data_forcomment.docx)

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[draft_standard_yield_data_forcomment < https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft_standard_yield_data_forcomment.docx>](https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft_standard_yield_data_forcomment.docx)

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[draft-standard-Magnetic-data-forcomment < https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft-standard-Magnetic-data-_v03.docx>](https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft-standard-Magnetic-data-forcomment-Magnetic-data-_v03.docx)

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[draft-standard-EMI-data_forcomment < https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft-standard-EMI-data_v03.docx>](https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft-standard-EMI-data_v03.docx)

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[draft-standard-GPR-data_forcomment < https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft-standard-GPR-data_v03.docx>](https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft-standard-GPR-data_v03.docx)

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[draft_standard_cropmark_data_forcomment < https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft_standard_cropmark_data_forcomment-1.docx>](https://ipaast-czo.glasgow.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/draft_standard_cropmark_data_forcomment-1.docx)

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Use this form to provide comments on the guidance. Submit one form per guidance document.

Comments on ipaast draft data guidance

* Required

1. Which data guide are you addressing? *

2. What is useful about the guidance?

Alternative link to the form: <https://forms.office.com/r/vEnVLhLDwN> <
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